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MIXED CONVECTION FLOW SIMULATION INSIDE 2D CAVITY PARTIALLY HEATED FILLED WITH HYBRID NANOFLUID

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ABSTRACT

The main challenge faced by many studies in Electronic components is the overheating which leads to adverted effects on their lifetime and electrical efficiency. Several efforts have been made to control this temperature through heat evacuation.

A Numerical Simulation of Mixed convection of Hybrid Nanofluid flow in two-dimensional cavity is carried out. The configuration consists of a cavity that is filled with Hybrid nanofluid possessing a heat source in the West wall (T_h). The cold Hybrid Nanofluid enters by a constant temperature to flow between the Sud wall and the heat source (T_c), while the remaining part remains in the adiabatic conditions. The volume fraction's influence on the heat transfer and thermal fields is examined by the finite volume method for several thermal parameters namely, Reynolds, Nusselt and Richardson numbers. The results revealed that the heat transfer's rate becomes important with Reynolds number and the volume fraction rise of Hybrid Nanofluids.

The Navier-Stokes equations and the energy governing the problem are discretized by the finite volume method, taking into account the Boussinesq approximation and neglecting the viscous dissipation. The conservation equations of momentum coupled with the continuity equation are solved using the SIMPLEC Algorithm. The resolution of the discretized algebraic system is based on the method of alternating directions (ADI). Interesting results has been found by proper choice of the governing parameters values and are presented in terms of isotherms, isolines, Nusselt Numbers and heat transfer rates.

Keywords: Numerical simulation; Hybrid Nanofluid; 2D Mixed convection.